

Effects of Proactive and Reactive Cognitive Control on Bilingual Language Switching

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A central distinction between monolingual and bilingual language processing lies in *parallel activation*: bilinguals simultaneously activate lexical representations in both their target and non-target languages (e.g., Costa et al., 1999; Kroll et al., 2012; Thierry & Wu, 2007). This parallel activation creates cross-language interference that must be resolved to enable fluent communication. The cognitive process responsible for regulating such interference is referred to as *language control* (Declerck & Koch, 2023; Runqvist et al., 2011).

The nature of language control has been debated over the past decades. The dominant view posits that bilingual language control relies on inhibitory mechanisms that suppress the non-target language, allowing accurate selection of the target language (Green, 1998; see Declerck & Koch, 2023, for a review). According to this account, the degree of inhibition applied to a language depends on its activation strength, with more dominant languages requiring stronger suppression.

Much of the empirical support for this inhibitory account comes from the language-switching paradigm, in which bilinguals switch between languages while naming pictures or digits. A robust finding is that responses are slower and more error-prone on switch trials than on repetition trials, known as the language switch cost (Bobb & Wodniecka, 2013; Declerck & Philipp, 2015). Switch costs are interpreted as reflecting the effort involved in selecting the target language and overcoming interference from the previously used language.

Critically, many studies report asymmetrical switch costs, whereby switching into the native language (L1) induces greater costs than switching into the second language (L2) (see Bobb & Wodniecka, 2013; Declerck & Koch, 2023; Declerck & Philipp, 2015). This pattern has been taken as evidence for inhibitory language control: because the dominant L1 is more

strongly suppressed when using L2, greater effort is required to reactivate it (Green, 1998; Meuter & Allport, 1999). As such, asymmetrical switch costs have supported the notion of proportional, reactive inhibition in bilingual language control.

Most empirical research, has focused on *reactive* inhibitory language control (Bobb & Wodniecka, 2013; Calabria et al., 2018; Declerck & Philipp, 2015, 2017; Meuter & Allport., 1999; Phillip et al., 2007). However, bilingual language control is believed to rely on both proactive and reactive mechanisms (Declerck et al., 2021; Ma et al., 2016; Peeters & Dijkstra, 2018; Seo & Prat, 2019; for reviews Declerck, 2020; Declerck & Koch,2023).

In this regard, *Dual Mechanisms of Control* (DMC) framework (Braver, 2012), characterizes executive control in terms of its internal variability. The DMC distinguishes between two modes of control: *proactive* and *reactive*. Proactive control is sustained and anticipatory, functioning as an “early selection” mechanism that actively maintains goal-relevant information to prevent interference before it occurs. Reactive control, in contrast, is transient and stimulus-driven, serving as a “late correction” mechanism that resolves conflict after its detection (Braver, 2012; Braver et al., 2009; Etzel et al., 2022; Paxton et al., 2008). This framework provides a dynamic account of variability in control strategies. Faster, more efficient performance typically reflects reliance on proactive control, whereas slower responses indicate greater dependence on reactive mechanisms (e.g., Dash et al., 2021). Applying this framework to bilingualism shifts the focus from binary “advantage” debates toward a more nuanced examination of how bilinguals engage distinct modes of control.

In terms of bilingual language control, researchers suggest that *reactive* language control is engaged after cross-language interference is detected and require rapid suppression of non-target language activation (Bobb & Wodniecka, 2013; Calabria et al., 2018; Declerck & Philipp, 2015, 2017; Meuter & Allport., 1999; Philipp et al., 2007). *Proactive* language control, in contrast, is anticipatory and involves preparatory adjustments to language activation levels to minimize interference before it arises. For instance, when speaking primarily in one language, representations from the other may be co-activated, producing interference (Declerck, 2020; Declerck & Koch, 2023). In such contexts, proactive downregulation of the non-target language may be required to maintain fluent speech and reduce cross-language intrusions.

Studies directly comparing bilingual and monolingual performance within the DMC framework remain limited and yield mixed results (Dash et al., 2021; Morales et al., 2013, 2015; Rainey et al., 2021). For example, using the AX-Continuous Performance Task (AX-CPT), Morales et al. (2013) found that bilinguals outperformed monolinguals on AY trials, suggesting lower reliance on proactive control. A subsequent ERP study replicated these behavioral findings and provided neural evidence (in N2, P3a, and error-related negativity components) indicating greater engagement of reactive control among bilinguals (Morales et al., 2015). Similarly, Bonfieni et al. (2020) reported that early, high-proficiency bilinguals performed better on AY trials than late or passive bilinguals, though this effect became marginal when individual variability was accounted for in a mixed-effects model.

In contrast, Dash et al. (2021) found that older bilinguals showed more efficient proactive control during the Simon task, accompanied by reduced brain activation compared to age-matched monolinguals. Rainey et al. (2021) also reported neural evidence that bilinguals engaged both control modes more effectively, showing increased sustained potentials (proactive

control) and reduced N450 amplitudes (reactive control) during Stroop conflict trials. Conversely, Declerck et al. (2021) found no evidence of proactive control in a bilingual picture-naming task. Taken together, these findings suggest that bilinguals may not consistently favor one control mode but instead flexibly adapt their strategies.

To address these inconsistent findings, the present study moves beyond group comparisons and instead directly examines whether bilinguals differ in their engagement of proactive and reactive control during language switching and repetition. Participants will complete the AX Continuous Performance Task (AX-CPT; Rosvold et al., 1956) in combination with a language-switching task. This approach enables a comprehensive assessment of dual mechanisms of control (DMC) in both switching and repetition contexts, allowing us to determine whether bilingual language control preferentially relies on a specific control mechanism during switching versus repetition, and whether this pattern differs between L1 and L2.

Method

This study was approved by the Hacettepe University Social Sciences and Humanities Research Ethics Committee. Each participant will provide written informed consent before participation.

Study Design

Bilingual participants completed the combined language switching and AX-CP task. The study employs a within-subjects design, with *language* (L1 vs. L2), *switch type* (language switch vs. repeat) and *trial type* (AY, BX and BY). The study also investigates performance on AX trials with *language* (L1 vs. L2), *switch type* (language switch vs. repeat) as within-subjects factors. Analyses focus on differences in reaction times and accuracy rates across these factors.

Participants

The study sample will include bilingual participants, all of whom speak Turkish as their native language (L1) and English as their second language (L2). The study aims to recruit at least 20 participants. Participant classification as bilingual will be determined using the Language and Social Background Questionnaire (Anderson et al., 2018).

Other inclusion criteria require participants to be 18-30 years old, currently enrolled in or graduated from a higher education program, have no psychiatric or neurological history, and report no regular use of psychiatric medication or psychoactive substances in the past few months.

Data Collection Instruments

Language and Social Background Questionnaire (LSBQ)

The Turkish version of the LSBQ will be used to identify bilingual and monolingual participants. The original questionnaire was developed by Anderson et al. (2018). It was previously translated into Turkish by Tomić et al. (2023), and our independent translation closely matched theirs.

The LSBQ consists of three sections: Demographic Information, Language Background, and Community Language Use Behavior. The first section does not contribute directly to bilingualism scoring; it only collects demographic data. The second section assesses known languages, age and context of acquisition, proficiency across four language skills, and degree of language exposure. The third section examines language use across life periods, interlocutors, and frequency of language switching.

Responses from the second and third sections yield three factor scores (L2 home use and proficiency, L2 social use, and L1 proficiency) and one *composite score*. According to Anderson

et al. (2018), individuals with a *composite factor score* of ≥ 1.2 are classified as bilingual, and those scoring ≤ -3.1 as monolingual. In our study, participants who score > 1.2 will be invited to complete the experimental task.

Combined Language Switching and AX-Continuous Performance Task (AX-CPT)

The AX-CPT is a cognitive paradigm assessing sustained attention and context processing (Rosvold et al., 1956). Although several variants exist (e.g., Chevalier et al., 2015, which uses nonverbal figures), the letter-based version is most common. In this version, participants view repeated cue–probe letter sequences and respond “yes” when the probe X follows the cue A, and “no” to all other combinations. The task includes four trial types: AX (cue= A; probe= X), AY (cue= A; probe= non-X letter, e.g., Y), BX (cue= non-A letter, e.g., B; probe= X), and BY (cue= non-A letter; probe= non-X letter).

According to the DMC framework, presentation of a cue triggers expectations about the upcoming probe. Proactive control relies on this cue-based anticipation: since different cues signal different likely outcomes, participants use the cue–probe delay to prepare an appropriate response. Typically, AX trials constitute most of the task (e.g., 70%), encouraging a prepotent tendency to respond “yes” after seeing the A cue. Over time, the A cue becomes strongly associated with the X probe, leading participants to prepare a “yes” response during the delay. Conversely, a B cue, prompts preparation of a “no” response.

This preparatory pattern systematically shapes performance across trial types. AY trials often disrupt performance because participants anticipate an X but encounter a different probe, requiring inhibition of the prepotent “yes” response. Higher error rates or slower responses on these trials are typically interpreted as evidence of stronger proactive control, since proactive strategies depend on maintaining and acting upon cue-based expectations (see Braver 2012). BX

trials are also challenging, as the X probe appears without being preceded by A, requiring suppression of the automatic “yes” response. In this case, better performance reflects greater reliance on proactive control, whereas increased errors suggest dependence on reactive control, in which participants primarily respond to the probe rather than anticipating based on the cue (see Braver 2012). In contrast, BY trials serve as control conditions, as neither the cue nor the probe elicits the dominant response tendency, providing a baseline for general task performance.

The present study will employ the AX-CPT adapted from Braver et al. (2021) (see also Etzel et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2023) and further modify using PsychoPy 3 software (Peirce, 2007). The primary distinction from Braver et al. (2021) concerns the nature of the stimuli: whereas the original version used letters, the present study will employ verbal stimuli (words) to enable language switching and repetition manipulation. Specifically, the words *kitab* and its English translation *book* will serve as the A cue, whereas *gemi* and its English translation *ship* as the X probe. Participants will be instructed to press the “no” button for all words except when *gemi* or *ship* appeared; in that case, they were to press “yes” only if *gemi* or *ship* was preceded by *kitab* or *book* (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Instructions

Note. Participants will be told that they can encounter four types of word pairs (1) kitap/book-gemi/ship, (2) kitap/book-other, (3) other-gemi/ship, and (4) other-other. They need to press “no” (in Turkish “hayır”) to all pairs, except the (1) kitap/book-gemi/ship. In that case they need to press “yes” (in Turkish “evet”). They will also be told that kitap-gemi, kitap-ship, book-gemi, and book-ship are all included in this exception.

Critically, the cue and target words will be presented either in L1 or L2, which will enable to manipulate language switching. For instance, a kitap-gemi pair represents a L1 repeat trial, whereas a kitap-ship pair represents a switch to L2 trial. All language switching and repetition combinations (L1 repeat, L1 switch, L2 repeat, and L2 switch) will be presented proportionally across all trial types (AX, AY, BX, and BY).

Each trial will begin with the presentation of a cue word, which remains on screen until a response is made or until 1000 ms elapses. This will be followed by a 3000 ms delay. Afterward

a blank frame will be presented for 300 ms, and then the probe word will appear within this frame, which stays visible until a response is made or 1000 ms had elapses. A 1500 ms inter-trial interval will separate consecutive trials.

The task will consist of eight blocks. Each block including 16 trials: ten AX, two AY, two BX, and two BY trials. The order of trial types within each block will be randomized, except for the first trial, which will always be an AX filler trial. The full implementation of the task condition lasted about 16-18 minutes.

Before the main tasks, participants will complete practice blocks of 8–10 trials to ensure comprehension of the instructions and task structure. These practice trials will be identical to those in the main task in terms of visual presentation and timing, but will include immediate feedback after each response (e.g., “correct,” “incorrect,” or “no button pressed”). Participants will be allowed to repeat the practice block if needed.

The cue and probe words (*kitap-book*; *gemi-ship*) were matched on key psycholinguistic properties, including letter count, emotional valence, and, arousal. These particular words were chosen because they were both neutral in terms of emotional valence and arousal. Similarly, all other words used in the AX-CPT matched across these dimensions. The psycholinguistic characteristics of all words were extracted from Kapucu and colleagues (2021) and, Bradley and Lang (1999).

Procedure

The study will be conducted in the Psychology Laboratories of Hacettepe University. Participants will be recruited via university notice boards, student groups, and in-class announcements.

The research will consist of two stages. In the first stage, inclusion criteria were assessed using the Language and Social Background Scale, administered online via Google Forms.

Participants meeting the criteria will be invited to the second stage, conducted in person.

In the second stage, participants will complete the combined language switching and AX-SP task. Responses will be recorded using external numeric keypads of the same brand and specifications for all participants. The full procedure will last approximately 20 minutes.

Data analysis

Data Preprocessing

Reaction time (RT) data will be cleaned by removing filler and error trials. Outliers will be identified and removed separately for each task, participant, and condition using a ± 2.5 standard deviation criterion. These procedures will be implemented to minimize the influence of early trials, errors, and attentional lapses, thereby enhancing internal validity.

In the AX-CPT task, for analysis purposes, AY, BX, and BY trials will be combined into a single dataset, with trial type modeled as a three-level factor (AY, BX, BY), consistent with prior work (e.g., Bonfieni et al., 2020; Morales et al., 2013, 2015). Whereas, AX trials will be analyzed separately due to their distinct functional role.

Accuracy rates (AR) will also be computed as the proportion of correct responses.

Statistical Analyses

RT and AR performance will be analyzed using linear mixed-effects (LME) models (Bates et al., 2015b; Pinheiro et al., 2024). Fixed effects will include *language* (L1 vs. L2), *switch type* (switch vs. repeat), and *trial type* (AY, BX and BY). RT models will include random intercepts for *participant* and *trial*, while AR models included random intercepts for *participant* only. Also RT and AR in the AX trials will be analyzed using *language* (L1 vs. L2) and *switch*

type (switch vs. repeat) as fixed effects, and *participant* as random intercept effect. Random slopes will not be included in any analysis to maintain model parsimony (Bates et al., 2015a).

All LME analyses were conducted in RStudio (version 2023.12.1) using the `lme` function from `nlme` (v3.1-164) (Pinheiro et al., 2024). Statistical significance was assessed with the `anova` function from `lmerTest` (v3.1-3) (Kuznetsova et al., 2017). Effect sizes were estimated using `sjstats` (v0.19.0) (Lüdtke, 2018), and Bonferroni-corrected post hoc comparisons were conducted with `emmeans` (v1.10.6) (Lenth, 2023).

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